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WINDOWS FORMS .NET ILOVALARNING DIZAYNIDA UI/UX FRAMEWORKLARINING AFZALLIKLARI

***Annotatsiya:** .Net texnologiyasida Windows Forms ilovalarining interfeyslarini yaratishda, loyihalashda, dizaynida UI/UX freymvorklarning o'rni katta bo'lib, ular orqali yaratilayotgan ilovaning dizaynini sodda loyihalash mumkin.*

***Kalit so'zlar:** .Net texnologiyasi, freymvorklar, UI/UX, dizayn, button, boshqaruv elementlari, GUNA, Bunifu.*

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ADVANTAGES OF UI/UX FRAMEWORKS IN DESIGNING WINDOWS FORMS .NET APPLICATIONS

***Annotation:** UI/UX frameworks play a major role in creating, designing and designing the interfaces of Windows Forms applications in .Net technology and with the help of them one can easily design the design of the application being created.*

***Key words:** .Net technology, frameworks, UI/UX, design, button, control elements, GUNA, Bunifu.*

C# dasturlash tili asosiga qurilgan .Net texnologiyalarida Windows Form ilovalarini yaratish orqali ko'plab sohalarda mavjud masalalarni yechuvchi dasturlar va web ilovalar ommalashib bormoqda. Bu texnologiyalar orqali ko'plab boshqarish tizimlari, hisob-kitob tizimlari, ilovalar yaratish imkoni mavjud. Bu esa o'z navbatida ilovalarning dizaynini yaratishga bir qancha shartlar qo'yimoqda. Dasturchilar Winform ilovalarning dizaynini yaratishda standart boshqaruv elementlaridan foydalanishi va ularga ishlov berishida ko'plab qiyinchiliklar yuzaga kelishi mumkin. Shuningdek bu vazifalar dasturchidan ko'plab vaqt talab qilishi mumkin. Masalan birgina rangi, shakli, border radiusi kabi ko'plab xususiyatlari o'zgaruvchan bo'lgan Button elementini yaratish uchun quyidagi birqancha amallar ketma- ketligini bajarish zarur hisoblanadi. Ishni avvalo loyihaga yangi class qo'shishdan boshlashimiz zarur:

1-рasm.

Bu yerda yaratmoqchi bo‘lgan elementimizga nom beramiz, ya’ni yaratilgan sinf nomi va element nomi bir xil bo‘ladi. Yaratgan sinfimiz ichiga quyidagi kodlarni yozib chiqamiz:

```
using System.Windows.Forms;
using System.Drawing;
using System.Drawing.Drawing2D;
using System.ComponentModel;
namespace WindowsFormsApp21
{
    internal class RJButton:Button
    {
        private int borderSize = 0;
        private int borderRadius = 40;
        private Color borderColor = Color.PaleVioletRed;
        [Category("RJ Code Advance")]
        public int BorderSize { get => borderSize; set { borderSize = value;
this.Invalidate(); } }
        [Category("RJ Code Advance")]
        public int BorderRadius { get => borderRadius; set { borderRadius = value;
this.Invalidate(); } }
        [Category("RJ Code Advance")]
        public Color BorderColor { get => borderColor; set { borderColor = value;
this.Invalidate(); } }
        [Category("RJ Code Advance")]
        public Color
BackgroundColor {get=>this.BackColor;set{this.BackColor=value;}}
        [Category("RJ Code Advance")]
        public Color TextColor {get=>this.ForeColor;set{this.ForeColor = value; } }
        public RJButton()
        {
```

```

    this.FlatStyle = FlatStyle.Flat;
    this.FlatAppearance.BorderSize = 0;
    this.Size = new Size(150, 40);
    this.BackColor = Color.MediumSlateBlue;
    this.ForeColor = Color.White;
}
private GraphicsPath GetFigurePath( RectangleF rect, float radius)
{
    GraphicsPath path = new GraphicsPath();
    path.StartFigure();
    path.AddArc(rect.X, rect.Y, radius, radius, 180, 90);
    path.AddArc(rect.Width-radius, rect.Y, radius, radius, 270, 90);
    path.AddArc(rect.Width-radius, rect.Height-radius,radius,radius, 0, 90);
    path.AddArc(rect.X, rect.Height-radius, radius, radius, 90, 90);
    path.CloseFigure();
    return path;
}

protected override void OnPaint(PaintEventArgs pevent)
{
    base.OnPaint(pevent);
    pevent.Graphics.SmoothingMode = SmoothingMode.AntiAlias;

    RectangleF rectSurface = new RectangleF(0, 0, this.Width, this.Height);
    RectangleF rectBorder =new RectangleF(1,1,this.Width-0.8F,this.Height-
1);
    if(borderRadius > 2)
    {
        using(GraphicsPath pathSurface=GetFigurePath(rectSurface,
borderRadius))
        using(GraphicsPath pathBorder=GetFigurePath(rectBorder,borderRadius-
1F))
        using (Pen penSurfece = new Pen(this.Parent.BackColor,2))
        using (Pen penBorder = new Pen(borderColor, borderSize))
        {
            penBorder.Alignment = PenAlignment.Inset;
            this.Region = new Region(pathSurface);
            pevent.Graphics.DrawPath(penSurfece, pathSurface);

```

```

        if( borderSize >= 1)
            pevent.Graphics.DrawPath(penBorder, pathBorder);
    }} else {
        this.Region = new Region(rectSurface);
        if (borderSize >= 1)
        {
            using ( Pen penBorder = new Pen(borderColor, borderSize))
            {
                penBorder.Alignment = PenAlignment.Inset;
                pevent.Graphics.DrawRectangle(penBorder, 0, 0, this.Width - 1,
this.Height - 1);
            }
        }
    }
}
protected override void OnHandleCreated(EventArgs e)
{
    base.OnHandleCreated(e);

    this.Parent.BackColorChanged+=newEventHandler(Container_BackColorChange
d);
}
private void Container_BackColorChanged(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
    if(this.DesignMode)
        this.Invalidate();
}
}
}

```

Bu yerda yangi Button obykti yaratib olinib, uning BorderSize, BorderRadius, BorderColor, BackgroundColor, TextColor xossalarini o‘zgaruvchan qilib yozib chiqilgan.

Shundan so‘ng loyihamizni build qilganimizda yangi elementimiz elementlar panelida paydo bo‘ladi va biz undan foydalanishimiz mumkin.

2-рasm.

Аmmo zamonaviy .Net texnologiyalari asosida ishlab chiqilgan va UI/UX dizayndagi muammolarni yechish imkoni sifatida ko'plab UI/UX dizayn freymvorklar yaratilgan. Bu dasturchiga qisqa vaqt sarflab, ajoyib dizayndagi ilovalar yaratish imkonini beradi. Bularga DevExpress, MetroFramework, Materialskin, Bunifu Framework, GUNA Framework kabilar misol bo'la oladi.

Guna Frameworkni ko'rib chiqadigan bo'lsak, bu frameworkni biz <https://www.nuget.org/packages/Guna.UI2.WinForms/#versions-body-tab> saytidan ustanovochniy paketini olamiz va C:\Program Files (x86)\Microsoft SDKs\NuGetPackages\nuget.frameworks\4.6.4 papkaga yuklangan paketimizni joylashtiramiz. Yangi winform loyihasini yaratamiz va u yerdan proyekt papkasi ustiga o'ng tugma orqali NuGet paketlarini boshqarish bo'limiga o'tamiz, ko'rsatish (browse) bo'limiga o'tamiz va qidiruv qismiga guna deb yozamiz. Paydo bo'lgan Guna.UI2.WinForms paketini o'rnatamiz (1-rasm).

3-рasm.

O'rnatilgandan so'ng elementlar panelini tekshirsak yangi guna elementlari hosil bo'lganini ko'rishimiz mumkin.

4-рasm.

Hosil bo'lgan elementlardan foydalanishni boshlashimiz bilan bizga aktivatsiya oynasi ochiladi va bizdan litsenziya so'raydi. Biz bu freymvorkdan 14 kunlik sinov bersiyasi sifatida foydalanishimiz yoki to'lov qilib pulli versiyalarini sotib olishimiz mumkin. Bepul versiyani ustanovka qilish uchun trial tugmasini bosamiz va hosil bo'lgan oyna orqali ro'yxatdan o'tamiz.

Guna paketi orqali o'zimizning dizaynimizni yaratish imkoniga egamiz. Masalan birgina tugma(button)ning 7 xil turi mavjud. Bular: Guna2Button, Guna2CircleButton, Guna2GradientButton, Guna2GradientCircleButton, Guna2GradientTileButton, Guna2ImageButton, Guna2TileButton (3-rasm).

5-rasm.

Oddiy button va Guna2Buttonning farqini quyida ko'rishimiz mumkin:

6-rasm.

Guna orqali joylashtirilgan tugmaning ko'plab parametrlarini elementning yuqorisida joylashgan tugmani bosish orqali o'zgartirish mumkin. Bu esa ishning samaradorligini oshirish imkonini beradi.

Form oynasini ham o'z xohishingizga ko'ra qayta dizayn qilib chiqishingiz mumkin. Bunda boshqaruv oyna, menyular oynasi, asosiy oyna kabi o'zingizning dizayningizni loyihalashingiz mumkin.

Shunday qilib biz ikki xil usul yordamida o'zimizning ilovalarimiz dizaynini ishlab chiqishni ko'rdik. Ikkinchi usulimiz freymvork texnologiyalari orqali ishimiz sifati, tezligi va samaradorligini oshirish imkonini beradi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar.

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